

**Experimental investigation on treatment of real sugar industry wastewater using
Upflow Anaerobic Sludge Blanket (HUASB) Reactor**

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Abstract

In this paper the synthetic wastewaters of tapioca starch (SAGO) were treated using Hybrid Upflow Anaerobic Sludge Blanket (HUASB) reactor. The system was inoculated with seed sludge from the existing anaerobic digester treating sago wastewater. The processes were carried out first by feeding the synthetic sago wastewater with operating parameter such as Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD) ranging from 5200 to 6320 mgL⁻¹ with HRT 24 hours. The COD were varied from 5200, 5400, 5860 and 6320 mg/l for synthetic sago effluent. The pH, COD removal, Volatile Fatty Acid (VFA), Alkalinity and Biogas production were monitored for various inlet of COD concentrations. The inlet pH was maintained between the range 5.6, 6.1, 6.5, 6.8, 7.2 and 7.6 and the outlet pH were 6.9, 7.2, 7.6, 7.8, 8.0 and 8.2. The VFA varies from 32, 36, 40, 44, 52 and 56 mg/l, the alkalinity varies from 656, 668, 684, 698, 742 and 764 mg/l and the biogas production varies from 8.6 to 13.6 mg/l. The maximum COD removal of 89.2% and the biogas production was about 13.6 l/d at pH 7.6.

Key words: *HUASB, Synthetic, sago,*

1 Introduction

The interest in anaerobic wastewater treatment for environmental protection and recovery of renewable resources is increasing worldwide. The anaerobic biological sludge blanket systems proposed over recent years have elicited considerable interest because of their good removal efficiencies of organic substrates, their relatively simple layout and the low capital and operating costs. Granular biomass with high methanogenic activity and excellent settling properties can be cultivated in these reactors (Buzzini et al. 2006).

Over different types of anaerobic reactors, UASB reactor are generally more resistant to toxic compounds due to the formed granular sludge with good settling properties. Upflow anaerobic sludge blanket (UASB) reactors are used successfully for several types of industrial (high to medium strength) wastewaters and low-strength wastewaters (Lettinga et al. 1984; Singh et al. 1996; Agrawal et al. 1997; Seghezzi et al. 1998). The quality and stability of sludge directly dictates the behavior of the entire treatment system. Sago, the edible starch in the form of globules, is manufactured from tapioca tubers (*Mannihot Ulillisema*). In the southern region of India alone there are about 800 sago mills which were medium and large scale units producing 15 to 30 tonne of sago per unit per day. These units discharge about 40,000 to 50,000 litres of effluent per tonne of sago processed. Many investigators observed that the wastewater from sago mills is of serious concern from stream pollution point of view (Murthy and Patel, 1961; Saroja and Sastry 1972; Gnanapragasam et al. 2010, Senthilkumar et al. 2011). This study examines the feasibility of treatment of synthetic sago under pilot scale hybrid up-flow anaerobic sludge blanket reactor of stressed loadings. Shortening the start-up time bears practical significance as it can raise attractiveness of HUASB applications by saving time and cost. After the start-up process the operating parameters such as COD, pH and HRT were varied.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Biomass

The granular sludge with unknown microorganisms used in this experiment was obtained from the anaerobic digester treating tapioca starch effluent of M/s Perumal SAGO factory, Salem, Tamilnadu, India. Before loading the reactor, granular sludge was clearly washed, filtered through a fine mesh to reduce all the inorganic mineral contents. The volatile suspended solid content of the sludge was then estimated about 60000 mg/l (APHA 2005).

2.2 Wastewater

The synthetic sago wastewater were prepared by adding starch and minerals Nitrogen $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ and Phosphorous KH_2PO_4 were added with the COD: N: P ratio of 550:5:1. The stock solution of trace nutrients containing ferric chloride, zinc sulphate, copper sulphate etc. were added at a concentration of 1.0 ml /l of the feed solution to the reactor (Bhatt 1995; Arshad et al. 2009).

2.3 Experimental Setup

Owing to prior knowledge and the ample advantages of the HUASB reactor, it was decided to utilize a laboratory scale HUASB reactor for this study was designed and fabricated using Perspex tube. Reactor with effective volume of 20 L and the total height of the reactor was about 1.42 m. The effective height of the reactor was 1.17m and the diameter of the reactor 0.15 m, respectively. The solid-gas-liquid separator (GLSS) was also kept in the upper part of the reactor in the form of inverted conical funnel for bio gas collection to prevent the loss of granules from the reactor and for easy release of the gas produced by anaerobic digestion. The amount of gas produced is measured by water displacement method. A peristaltic pump (20ppm) with constant discharge flow was used to pump the substrate into the reactor. The top third segment of the reactor was filled with bio-ball as support media. 152 pieces of black bio-ball were used as attached growth media of the same size which has a diameter of about 2.8 cm, a specific area of $550 \text{ m}^2/\text{m}^3$, porosity hollow of 0.97. This bio-balls prevents the escape of bio granules from the reactor. Totally 5 sampling ports were installed for ease collect of sample for analysis at different heights. The reactor was operated at 31°C to 35°C .

3 Result and discussion

3.1 COD removal

The result obtained during the process run of different HRT was plotted in Figure 1. The HUASB reactor were fed with COD concentration from 5200 mg/l to 6320 mg/l at various HRT's. From the Figure 2 it is evident that COD removal efficiency was in the range of 69.2 % to 89.2 % in methanogenic reactor at various HRT's. The 89.2 % COD removal efficiency was achieved at 24 h HRT in methanogenic reactor and for the acidogenic reactor the maximum COD removal of 39.4 % was achieved at 36 h HRT. Rai et al. (2007) achieved the maximum removal (96 %) of COD by treating triphenylmethane dye-bath effluent in an integrated bench scale two stage anaerobic reactor. Bras et al. (2005) also reported that the maximum COD removal at 24 h of HRT was about 90 % treating monoazo and diazo dyes in bench scale UASB reactor. In this study the sago-dye mixed effluent was treated with 90 %

COD reduction. Snethilkumar et al. (2011) have reported that maximum removal of efficiency of 90% using UASB reactor of 250 L.

Figure 1: Concentration of COD

Figure 2: COD Removal efficiency

3.2 pH, VFA and Alkalinity

The changes in pH, VFA and alkalinity in effluent of the reactor at various HRTs are shown in figures 3, 4 and 6. From figure 3 it is clear the pH of the feed and HUASB reactor outlet are in the range of 6.5-6.8 and 6.9-8.2 respectively. The VFA in acidogenic and methanogenic reactor is shown in figure 4. The VFA in UASB reactor ranges from 32 to 56 mg/l are more or less same for all the HRTs. The almost constant value of VFA indicates the stable operation of reactors. The Figure 5 shows the change in alkalinity of HUASB reactors. The alkalinity values for methanogenic reactor vary from 656 mg/l to 764 mg/l. In this study

the values of pH, VFA and alkalinity was under control for the stable operation of the HUASB reactor. At 24 h of HRT high volatile fatty acid concentrations, low pH and high volatile fatty acids/bicarbonate alkalinity ratios in the effluent of reactor show the inhibition of methanogenic bacteria activity (Isik 2004).

Figure 3: pH of inlet and outlet at all HRTs

Figure 4: Concentration of VFA

Figure 5: Alkalinity of the reactor

3.3 Biogas

Biogas production at different hydraulic retention time for methanogenic reactor was shown in figure 6. From figure 6 it is clear that as the removal efficiency of COD increases biogas production increases. The maximum biogas production of 13.6 l/d was achieved at 24 h of HRT. Biogas production in relation to COD is about 0.4 m³/kg COD removed, corresponding to a methane production of 0.0136 m³ CH₄ per kg of COD removed. Biogas production is directly related to COD stabilization, for example without biogas production minimal COD removal occurs. Gnanapragasam et al (2010) had reported the maximum production of biogas was about 355 l/d at 24 h of HRT by recycling the treated wastewater for 250 L UASB reactor.

Figure 6: Biogas Production at various days

4 Conclusion

Laboratory scale hybrid upflow anaerobic sludge blanket reactor was used to synthetic sago wastewater as co-substrate at d=various concentration of COD. The maximum removal of COD achieved by the reactor is 89.2 % on fourth day of the reactor startup. The biogas production was maximum at 4th day with 13.6 l/d. The pH, VFA and alkalinity of the reactor effluent was stable under 24 h of HRT. From the results obtained it was clear UASB could be a very feasible alternative, eco –friendly and sustainable treatment system for synthetic sago effluent, which produce very less organic sludge and are comparable with the present conventional physiochemical treatment system which produce huge quantity of hazardous sludge, which requires further treatment and safe disposal.

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